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Structural and spectroscopic studies of the lithium tetraborate glass co-doped with Sm and Cu

B.V. Padlyak^{a,b}, I.I. Kindrat^{b*}, V.T. Adamiv^a, A. Drzewiecki^b, B. Cieniek^c, I. Stefaniuk^c

^a *Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Vlokh Institute of Physical Optics,
23 Dragomanov Str., 79-005 Lviv, Ukraine*

^b *University of Zielona Góra, Institute of Physics,
4a Szafrana Str., 65-516 Zielona Góra, Poland*

^c *University of Rzeszów, Institute of Materials Engineering,
16a Rejtana Str., 35-310 Rzeszów, Poland*

Abstract. The local structure and spectroscopic properties of the Cu-Sm co-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass have been studied by XRD, EPR, UV-Vis-NIR absorption and luminescence methods and compared with corresponding results for Sm-doped and Cu-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glasses. The EPR spectrum reveals an axially-symmetric signal with a characteristic hyperfine structure belonging to Cu^{2+} ions. The $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Cu}_{\text{total}}$ ratio was determined. The optical absorption spectrum shows a broad intense band attributed to Cu^{2+} ions and several weaker narrow bands attributed to Sm^{3+} ions. Photoluminescence (PL) and photoluminescence excitation (PLE) spectra and PL decay kinetics of Sm^{3+} and Cu^+ ions were registered, analyzed, and discussed. The PL spectra show a broad band assigned to the $3d^9 4s^1 \rightarrow 3d^{10}$ transition of Cu^+ ions and 4 narrow bands assigned to the $^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6\text{H}_J$ ($J = 5/2 - 11/2$) transitions of Sm^{3+} ions. The observed changes in PL intensity, shortening of the Sm^{3+} lifetime and prolongation of the Cu^+ lifetime were explained by energy transfer $\text{Sm}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^+$ and re-absorption of the Sm^{3+} emission by Cu^{2+} ions.

Keywords: borate glasses; Sm^{3+} ions; Cu^+ and Cu^{2+} ions; photoluminescence; energy transfer.

* Corresponding author. E-mail: igor.k.physics@gmail.com, I.Kindrat@if.uz.zgora.pl

1. Introduction

Presently, the study of borate glasses reveals significant scientific and practical interest.¹⁻³ There are two reasons for this interest. First, the borate glasses are more favorable materials than corresponding crystals due to the uncomplicated and low-cost glass technology. Second, the borate glasses can be doped with lanthanide ions in high amounts that is practically impossible for the corresponding borate crystals. It is well-known that the lanthanide ions show very efficient luminescence.^{4,5} As a result, materials activated with rare-earth ions, including Sm^{3+} ions, have modern practical applications, especially for solid-state lighting and laser technology.^{4,5} Luminescence of Sm^{3+} ($4f^5$, $^6\text{H}_{5/2}$) ions is focused on characteristic yellow, orange, and red emission bands belonging to the $^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6\text{H}_{5/2}$, $^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6\text{H}_{7/2}$, and $^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6\text{H}_{9/2}$ transitions, respectively. Therefore, it is important to combine the technological benefits of borate glasses with the efficient visible luminescence of Sm^{3+} ions in them.

Luminescent properties of the Sm-doped borate glasses with different basic compositions ($\text{Li}_2\text{O}-2\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$, $0.5\text{K}_2\text{O}-0.5\text{Li}_2\text{O}-2\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{CaO}-2\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$, $0.5\text{Li}_2\text{O}-\text{CaO}-0.5\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$) and different Sm_2O_3 doping concentrations have been studied in detail by us.⁶⁻⁸ Attractive results showed the Sm-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{O}-2\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ glass that revealed the highest PL quantum yield among the studied glasses.⁸ One can notice that the chemical composition of the $\text{Li}_2\text{O}-2\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ glass is identical to that of the well-known $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal.⁹ Therefore, the Sm-doped glass with the chemical formula $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ is detailed studied in this article. It is also worth noting that luminescent properties of Sm^{3+} ions in borate glasses of different compositions have been widely studied also by other authors and reported in numerous articles.¹⁰⁻¹²

Results obtained by us⁶⁻⁸ and other authors¹⁰⁻¹² point out that practical approaches for luminescence excitation in Sm-doped oxide glasses should receive considerable attention. Sm^{3+} ions in oxide glasses, including borate glasses, show narrow and relatively weak absorption in the UV-visible spectral region as a result of the parity-forbidden nature of $4f-4f$ transitions. Very often, the emission of pumping LEDs is broader than the absorption of Sm^{3+} ions. So, it is difficult to obtain the powerful light output of luminescence if the absorption is relatively weak, even for materials

with high PL quantum yield. Therefore, the study of additional mechanisms will be very useful to improve the excitation of Sm^{3+} ions and increase the light output.

For this reason, the effect of silver (Ag) co-doping on enhancing Sm^{3+} luminescence in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm},\text{Ag}$ glass was investigated by us.¹³ In particular, the article¹³ was devoted to analysis of the PL quantum yield and mechanisms related to enhancing of the Sm^{3+} photoluminescence. In the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm},\text{Ag}$ glass, the Sm^{3+} luminescence enhancement was achieved due to transfer of energy from the Ag^+ ions and the small non-plasmonic Ag_m^{n+} nanoclusters to Sm^{3+} ions.¹³ The absolute external quantum yield of Sm^{3+} luminescence in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm},\text{Ag}$ glass was grown on 42.6% comparing to the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass.¹³

Electron configurations of silver and copper are very similar with difference in the period only. In particular, $4d^{10}5s^1$ corresponds to neutral Ag atom and $3d^{10}4s^1$ corresponds to neutral Cu atom. A question arises whether the co-doping with Cu will also improve the Sm^{3+} luminescence. Accordingly, the subject of this article is a comprehensive research of spectroscopic and luminescent properties of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass. Obtained results will be compared with the corresponding findings gained by us for the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}^{6-8}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}^{14-16}$ glasses. A brief summary of our articles⁶⁻⁸ was given above. Results of studies of the Cu-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ and KLiB_4O_7 glasses were published by us.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ It was found that copper incorporates into the network of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ and KLiB_4O_7 glasses as Cu^{2+} ($3d^9$) and Cu^+ ($3d^{10}$) ions with characteristic electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR), optical absorption and PL graphs.¹⁴⁻¹⁶

Let us make a brief overview of published papers concerning to spectroscopy of Cu-Sm co-doped glasses. It should be noted that Cu-Sm co-doped glasses are studied insufficiently. In particular, a search in Scopus shows that the number of documents related to “ Sm^{3+} Cu glass” is 3 times less than that related to “ Sm^{3+} Ag glass”. Prior to the present time, spectroscopy of Cu-Sm co-doped glasses were published¹⁷⁻²⁰ and concern to silicate^{17,18}, phosphate¹⁹, and borosilicate²⁰ glasses. Published results are very controversial. The $\text{Cu}^+ \rightarrow \text{Sm}^{3+}$ energy transfer and the possibility of emission tuning in a wide spectral range were observed in Cu-Sm co-doped silicate-based glasses.^{17,18} However, the quenching of Sm^{3+} emission was observed in Cu-Sm co-doped

phosphate¹⁹ and borosilicate²⁰ glasses. The influence of CuO co-doping on the Sm³⁺ luminescence in 25Li₂O–25BaO–50B₂O₃ glass was reported in 2022 by Jiménez.²¹ It was concluded that further studies are needed with a focus on minimizing of the quenching of the Sm³⁺ luminescence and maximizing the Sm³⁺ emission for possible device applications.²¹ The overview of the available published data demonstrates that influence of the Cu dopant on Sm³⁺ luminescent properties in borate glasses has not been investigated yet in detail. Consequently, the principal objective of this work is to examine the effect of simultaneous Cu and Sm co-doping on the luminescence properties of these dopants in the Li₂B₄O₇ glass. The decision to prepare the Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glass instead of phosphor is based on the desired properties of the material. The investigated glass is a bulk sample and has better chemical and mechanical stability and protection from external factors such as moisture than the corresponding phosphor. In addition, the glass can be easily prepared into various shapes, sizes and thicknesses.

Prepared Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glass can have several potential applications, including: optoelectronics, scintillators, and energy conversion. The broad blue emission associated with Cu⁺ ions and the narrow yellow-red emission attributed to Sm³⁺ ions can contribute to the development of efficient and tunable light sources. The investigated glass can be suitable for use as a material for the detection of high energy radiation and elementary particles, including neutrons. The investigated glass can be used as a conversion layer in solar cells, because the ability to absorb and emit light across a wide range of wavelengths can improve the efficiency of energy conversion processes.

The novelty of this article lies in the study of the Cu-Sm co-doped Li₂B₄O₇ glass in comparison with the corresponding Cu-doped and Sm-doped glasses. The structural features, EPR spectra, optical absorption and photoluminescence properties are investigated, shedding light on the energy transfer between Sm and Cu dopants. The obtained results provide valuable insights into the properties of glasses co-doped with Cu and Sm and contribute to potential advances in optoelectronic applications.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Synthesis of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass and samples preparation

The $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass was prepared utilizing the melt-quenching technology.²² For obtaining of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ compound were used lithium carbonate, Li_2CO_3 (Sigma Aldrich, $\geq 99.9\%$) and boric acid, H_3BO_3 (Sigma Aldrich, 99.97%). The Cu and Sm were added to the glass composition as copper (II) oxide, CuO (Sigma Aldrich, 99.99%) and samarium (III) oxide, Sm_2O_3 (Sigma Aldrich, 99.999%) in amounts equal 1.0 mol.%. After thorough mixing of the raw materials in stoichiometric proportions, they were loaded into a corundum crucible and put in an electric furnace for the melting. This was done by heating to 1000°C and holding for 30 minutes. After this, the Cu-Sm co-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass was obtained by fast melt cooling. The process of glass preparing took place entirely in the air. The technological process of obtaining of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass can be represented as follows:

The same technological process was used to prepare the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ glasses.^{6,14} The Li_2CO_3 , H_3BO_3 and CuO or Sm_2O_3 were used as raw materials. The melting and cooling of the melts were carried out similarly to the multi-step chemical reactions (1). In particular, the temperatures of the corresponding stages, heating and cooling rates were the same as for the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass. The obtained $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass has a blue-green shade, whereas the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass is colorless (see Fig. 1).

The obtained glass samples were cut into two different sizes, approximately $12 \text{ mm} \times 8 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$ and $3 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm} \times 2 \text{ mm}$. Samples of larger size after polishing were used for recording of the optical absorption, PL and PLE spectra, and PL decay kinetics. Samples of smaller size were used for studies by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and EPR methods.

2.2. Research methods and tools

XRD pattern was registered using X-ray diffractometer of DRON-3 type. This diffractometer uses Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) and the measurement process is controlled by a computer. Paramagnetic centres in the Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glass were investigated using Bruker multi-frequency and multi-resonance FT-EPR spectrometer (model ELEXSYS-E580) operating in the X-band ($\nu \cong 9.850 \text{ GHz}$). Bruker's Xepr software was used to control the spectrometer and record the EPR spectra. Simulation and fitting of the EPR spectrum of Cu²⁺ ions was carried out using the EasySpin package, which is an open-source MATLAB toolbox.

Optical absorption spectra were recorded by the Shimadzu spectrophotometer (model UV-2600). It contains halogen and deuterium lamps, single-grating monochromator and the ISR-2600 Plus attachment. The PL and PLE spectra and PL decay kinetics were recorded with usage of the Horiba commercial spectrofluorimeter (model FluoroMax-4P). It contains a 150 W xenon lamp, two monochromators and the R928P photomultiplier.

All experiments were conducted at room temperature conditions with $T = 295 \text{ K}$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. XRD analysis

XRD pattern of the obtained Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm sample is shown in Fig. 2. There are no narrow crystalline peaks corresponding to the crystalline phase of Li₂B₄O₇ (see experimental XRD pattern in Fig. 2). The smooth XRD curve confirms the disordered glassy structure of the studied sample. There is a close resemblance between the broad peaks present in the XRD pattern of the Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glass and the positions and magnitudes of the dominant theoretical lines of the Li₂B₄O₇ crystal. There is also a sharp peak at 18 nm^{-1} (see Fig. 2), which cannot be related to Li₂B₄O₇. This peak is due to a marginal portion of SiO₂ impurity introduced from the crucible during the melting.

Registered XRD curve was analyzed to obtain local structure details, including the distances between the atoms and the coordination numbers. Intensity of scattered radiation of a system of N

atoms is expressed by the following formula:

$$I(s) = NF^2(s) \left\{ 1 + \int_0^{\infty} 4\pi r^2 [\rho(r) - \rho_0] \frac{\sin sr}{sr} ds \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where $s = 4\pi \sin \theta / \lambda$ is the scattering vector, $F^2(s)$ is the atomic scattering factor, r is the distance, $\rho(r)$ and ρ_0 are the real and average atomic density, respectively. From the Fourier-transformed equation (2), it is possible to obtain the radial distribution function:²³

$$4\pi r^2 \rho(r) = 4\pi r^2 \rho_0 + \frac{2r}{\pi} \cdot \int_{s_1}^{s_2} s \left[\frac{I(s)}{NF^2(s)} - 1 \right] \sin(sr) ds. \quad (3)$$

The radial distribution function $4\pi r^2 \rho(r)$ defines how the atomic density changes with the distance r .

The calculated radial distribution function, together with its deconvolution into partial components, is shown in Fig. 3. The average interatomic distances for specific atom pairs of different coordination spheres in the investigated glass network are also indicated in Fig. 3. It should be noted that interatomic distances in the second, third and fourth coordination spheres have not become the subject of in-depth analysis in this article, because the corresponding peaks at longer distances overlap with other atom pairs (see Fig. 3).

Therefore, only the average boron-oxygen and lithium-oxygen distances and the number of ligands for boron and lithium atoms in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass network are presented in Table 1. The coordination numbers for the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass were calculated by integration of corresponding deconvoluted components (Fig. 3). Additionally, Table 1 includes a comparison with corresponding distances ($r_{\text{B-O}}$, $r_{\text{Li-O}}$) and coordination numbers ($N_{\text{B-O}}$, $N_{\text{Li-O}}$) in the undoped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass network²² as well as the exact distances ($r_{\text{B-O}}$, $r_{\text{Li-O}}$), average distances ($r_{\text{B-O}}^{\text{av}}$), and coordination numbers ($N_{\text{B-O}}$, $N_{\text{Li-O}}$) in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal lattice²⁴.

As can be seen from Table 1, the $r_{\text{B-O}}^{\text{av}}$ distances in triangular ($N_{\text{B-O}} = 3$) and tetrahedral ($N_{\text{B-O}} = 4$) sites together with the $r_{\text{Li-O}}$ distance in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal²⁴ are significantly smaller than the $r_{\text{B-O}}$ and $r_{\text{Li-O}}$ distances in the investigated $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass and the undoped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass²². Also, the obtained distances in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass are slightly smaller than the $r_{\text{B-O}}$ and $r_{\text{Li-O}}$

distances in the undoped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass. The difference is not very large, especially when the uncertainty is taken into account (see Table 1). Nevertheless, it could be declared that incorporation of Cu and Sm dopants into the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass network causes a small compression (squeezing) of BO_n ($n = 3 - 4$) and LiO_n ($n = 4 - 6$) units in comparison with undoped glass of the same basic composition.

It is important to note that obtaining of the radial distribution function from XRD is a common practice for structural study of non-crystalline materials.^{23,25} The shape of the obtained radial distribution function of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7\text{:Cu,Sm}$ glass agrees with that of the $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass²⁵, where the first peak at 1.40 Å (0.140 nm) was attributed to the B–O distance and the second peak at 2.40 Å (0.240 nm) was attributed to the overlap of Na–O and O–O distances.

On the basis of the XRD studies, it can be argued that the glass-forming units in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7\text{:Cu,Sm}$ glass network include BO_3 triangles and BO_4 tetrahedra. The Li atoms with a coordination number $N_{\text{Li-O}}$ ranging from 4 to 6 act as modifiers of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7\text{:Cu,Sm}$ glass network. The structural data derived for the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7\text{:Cu,Sm}$ glass are in satisfactory agreement with the relevant data for the undoped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass²² and crystal²⁴. In particular, the local environment of the B and Li atoms in the investigated $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7\text{:Cu,Sm}$ glass, undoped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass²² and crystal²⁴ is similar. However, the BO_n ($n = 3 - 4$) and LiO_n ($n = 4 - 6$) units in the network of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7\text{:Cu,Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glasses show significant distortions with a wider range of structural parameters than those in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal lattice.

3.2. EPR spectroscopy

Experimental X-band EPR spectrum at $T = 295$ K indicates the appearance in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7\text{:Cu,Sm}$ glass of a characteristic signal, which is denoted and identified in Figs. 4 (A) and 4 (B). This complex non-isotropic EPR signal in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7\text{:Cu,Sm}$ glass (see Figs. (A, B)) is commonly observed in oxide glasses containing copper and belongs to Cu^{2+} ($3d^9$, $^2D_{5/2}$) paramagnetic ions.^{14–16,26–28} The EPR signal attributed to Cu^{2+} ions consists of two distinct groups of lines. Each group contains four barely resolved hyperfine components (see Figs. 4 (A, B)) due to

nuclei of the stable isotopes ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu (nuclear spin $I = 3/2$) with natural abundances of 69.17 % and 30.83 %, respectively. It should be noted that the hyperfine components caused by ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu nuclei are unresolved in the EPR spectrum (Figs. 4 (A, B)) due to the proximity of the ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu nuclear magnetic moments ($\mu(^{63}\text{Cu}) = 2.43$ and $\mu(^{65}\text{Cu}) = 2.54$).²⁹ Possibility of resolution of the hyperfine components caused by ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu isotopes is also limited by a significant inhomogeneous broadening of the EPR lines due to disordered structure of the investigated glass.

Observed axially-symmetric EPR spectrum of Cu^{2+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass has been satisfactorily described by the spin Hamiltonian:

$$\hat{H} = g_{\parallel}\mu_B H_z \hat{S}_z + g_{\perp}\mu_B (H_x \hat{S}_x + H_y \hat{S}_y) + A_{\parallel} \hat{S}_z \hat{I}_z + A_{\perp} (\hat{S}_x \hat{I}_x + \hat{S}_y \hat{I}_y), \quad (4)$$

where $g_{\parallel} = g_{zz}$, $g_{\perp} = g_{xx} = g_{yy}$ and $A_{\parallel} = A_{zz}$, $A_{\perp} = A_{xx} = A_{yy}$ are components of the axial g -tensor and A -tensor, respectively, μ_B is the Bohr magneton, H_x, H_y, H_z are components of the vector of the external magnetic field strength \mathbf{H} , $\hat{S}_x, \hat{S}_y, \hat{S}_z, \hat{I}_x, \hat{I}_y, \hat{I}_z$ are components of vectors of the electron and nuclear spin operators \hat{S} and \hat{I} , respectively.

Comparison of experimental and simulated axial EPR spectra of Cu^{2+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass are given in Fig. 5. Simulation and fitting allow to obtain more accurate values of the spin Hamiltonian parameters ($g_{\parallel}, g_{\perp}, A_{\parallel}, A_{\perp}$) and linewidths of peak-to-peak components of the hyperfine structure ($\Delta H_{\text{pp}}^{\parallel}$ and $\Delta H_{\text{pp}}^{\perp}$). The obtained $g_{\parallel}, g_{\perp}, A_{\parallel}, A_{\perp}, \Delta H_{\text{pp}}^{\parallel}$, and $\Delta H_{\text{pp}}^{\perp}$ parameters for Cu^{2+} ions are given in Table 2. Corresponding EPR spectra parameters obtained by us for Cu^{2+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ glasses with 0.4 mol.%^{14,15} and 1.6 mol.%¹⁶ of CuO also are presented in Table 2 for comparison.

In both $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ glasses, the g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} parameters exhibit close similarity. The relationship $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e = 2.0023$, where g_e is the g -factor of a free electron, indicates that an elongated (along the z -axis) octahedron is formed by six O^{2-} ligands.^{14–16,26–28} Thus, the Cu^{2+} ($3d^9, {}^2D_{5/2}$) ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ glasses exhibit the distortion of the octahedral geometry known as the Jahn-Teller effect.

There are some differences between the values of $A_{\parallel}, A_{\perp}, \Delta H_{\text{pp}}^{\parallel}$, and $\Delta H_{\text{pp}}^{\perp}$ for Cu^{2+} ions in the

$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ glasses. The A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} parameters are smaller in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass compared to the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ glass. This is due to higher delocalisation of d -electrons from ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu nuclei in the investigated glass. In addition, the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass shows lower linewidth values ($\Delta H_{\text{pp}}^{\parallel}$ and $\Delta H_{\text{pp}}^{\perp}$) compared to those observed in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ glass. This divergence is due to weaker dipole-dipole interaction between Cu^{2+} ions in the Cu-Sm co-doped glass comparing with the Cu-doped glass.

As will be shown below by luminescence spectroscopy, the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass contains not only Cu^{2+} ions but also Cu^+ ions. Therefore, the absolute quantitative EPR method, realized on the Bruker E580 spectrometer, was used to quantify the Cu^{2+} centers in the investigated glass. The number of unpaired electron spins is 3.25×10^{17} in the sample with a weight of 0.014941 g. This gives 2.175×10^{19} spins/g. In 1 mole of the investigated glass there are 3.011×10^{21} Cu atoms (or ions). Taking into account the molar mass of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass, in 1 g of the investigated glass there are 5.058×10^{19} Cu atoms (or ions). Thus, the ratio of Cu^{2+} amount to total Cu amount ($\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Cu}_{\text{total}}$) equals 43%.

Besides the Cu^{2+} EPR signal, a single EPR line with an isotropic effective g -factor $g_{\text{iso}} \cong 4.29$ is observed in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass and labeled as Fe^{3+} (1) in Fig. 4 (A). This signal is typical for glassy hosts and belongs to the uncontrolled Fe^{3+} ($3d^5$, $^6\text{S}_{5/2}$) paramagnetic ions.³⁰⁻³² The observed Fe^{3+} (1) EPR signal is in good agreement with signals previously registered in glasses with different basic compositions.^{14,15,33-36} Let us discuss the nature of the Fe^{3+} EPR signal.

The first interpretation of the EPR line showing g -factor near 4.29 in glasses was presented³⁰ coming from the analysis of the spin Hamiltonian given³⁷ in the following form:

$$\hat{H} = \mu_B \cdot (\mathbf{H} \cdot \mathbf{g} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{S}}) + D[S_z^2 - 1/3S(S+1)] + E(S_x^2 - S_y^2) \quad (5)$$

where D and E represent the axial and orthorhombic crystal field parameters, respectively. Nowadays, it is recognised³⁰⁻³⁶ that the EPR line with $g_{\text{iso}} \cong 4.29$ arises from single $3d^5$ ions, in particular Fe^{3+} and Mn^{2+} . Furthermore, the ratio $|E/D|$ should be near 1/3, which is the maximum that characterizes fully rhombic symmetry. Consequently, the Fe^{3+} (1) EPR line with $g_{\text{iso}} \cong 4.29$ in accordance with articles³⁰⁻³⁶ belongs to uncontrolled Fe^{3+} ions that are localized in octahedral

and/or tetrahedral sites with a significant (almost complete) rhombic distortion. It is important to note that Fe^{3+} EPR line with $g_{\text{iso}} \cong 4.29$ is typical for a glass structure.^{30,31,33–36} Thus, the presence of this line is an additional indication of the glassy structure of the material being studied, which confirmed also by the XRD pattern depicted above.

Faint sharp EPR line with $g_{\text{iso}} \cong 2.00$, labeled as Fe^{3+} (2) in Fig. 4 (B) and Fig. 5, which is also observed in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass in accordance with articles^{15,31,33} originates from a small part of Fe^{3+} ions, which are localized in the minimally distorted (almost cubic) sites of a glass network.

It is important to note that Fe^{3+} ions are not evident in the optical absorption spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass, because their concentration is low and their forbidden transitions are undetectable at small content of uncontrolled iron impurity. The quantity of uncontrolled iron impurity in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass has not been analytically determined, but our previous work⁶ shows that the iron content in Sm-doped borate glasses is 0.01 – 0.02 mol.%. The strong magnetic properties of iron impurity make it possible to observe EPR signals from uncontrolled Fe^{3+} ions even at very low concentrations.

3.3. Optical absorption

Optical absorption spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses are shown in Fig. 6. The spectrum of the Cu-containing glass reveals a broad strong band with a peak at 767 nm (13038 cm^{-1}) and a full width at half maximum (FWHM) 369 nm (6026 cm^{-1}). This absorption band belongs to Cu^{2+} ions ($3d^9$ electron configuration). The formation of a regular octahedral geometry (O_h group) in the glass network is attributed to the Cu^{2+} ion that is surrounded by six O^{2-} anions. In this situation, the crystal field induces the split of the ^2D ground term of Cu^{2+} ions onto $^2\text{E}_g$ and $^2\text{T}_{2g}$ levels. But, in the glass network very often is noticed the Jahn-Teller effect, which emphasizes a deformation of the regular octahedron. For the shortened or elongated octahedron (D_{4h} group) the $^2\text{E}_g$ state splits onto the $^2\text{B}_{1g}$ and $^2\text{A}_{1g}$ levels, while the $^2\text{T}_{2g}$ state splits onto the $^2\text{B}_{2g}$ and $^2\text{E}_g$ levels. The EPR spectroscopy gives valuable information concerning the local structure of Cu^{2+} ions. According to EPR data analysis, $g_{\perp} > g_{\parallel}$ and $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ indicate the shortened and elongated

octahedrons, respectively. According to the EPR outcomes presented in *Subsection 3.2*, it can be argued that Cu^{2+} ions form the elongated octahedron in the structure of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass. Thus, the broad band with a peak at 767 nm is assigned to the superposition of the ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$, ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$, and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ transitions. It is noteworthy that obtained results of optical absorption well correlate with references^{38–40}, in which the absorption of Cu^{2+} ions in oxide glasses reveals a peak in the 750 – 820 nm spectral region.

The Sm^{3+} ions ($4f^5$ electron configuration) show weak narrow absorption bands with peaks at 374 nm (${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{7/2}$ transition), 401 nm (${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$ transition), 460–480 nm (${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{9/2-15/2}$ transitions), 1074 nm (${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{9/2}$ transition), 1221 nm (${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{7/2}$ transition), and 1364 nm (${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{5/2}$ transition) (see insets in Fig. 6). At 401 nm is peaked the most intense absorption band of Sm^{3+} ions ascribed to the ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$ transition. Hence, the optical absorption spectroscopy clearly confirms the presence of Sm^{3+} and Cu^{2+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass. The O^{2-} anions form an elongated octahedra around the Cu^{2+} cations in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass network.

The fundamental absorption edge spans from 390 nm to 310 – 300 nm, where there is a rapid increase in absorbance. A shift of the fundamental absorption edge near 10 nm towards the longer wavelengths can be observed in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass comparing with the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass (see Fig. 6). The red shift of the fundamental absorption edge can be caused by the additional modification of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass host properties due to co-doping with CuO as well as by the influence of Cu^+ ions, which show the $3d^{10} \rightarrow 3d^9 4s^1$ transition in the UV spectral range.

The optical band gap (E_g^{opt}) of the investigated glass was assessed according to the approach firstly proposed by Tauc *et al.*⁴¹. In particular, the fundamental absorption edge in the case of indirect allowed band-to-band transition⁴² is described as follows:

$$\alpha h\nu = k(h\nu - E_g^{opt})^2, \quad (6)$$

where $\alpha h\nu$ is the product of absorption coefficient and photon energy, k is a constant. From the formula (6) it is noticeable that the fundamental absorption edge should be linear in the dependence of $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ on $h\nu$ and the optical band gap corresponds to the point where the linear fit of the fundamental absorption edge crosses the x -axis (see Fig. 7 (A)). For the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ and

$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses, the following E_g^{opt} values were obtained: 3.33 ± 0.03 eV and 3.38 ± 0.03 eV, respectively. Therefore, the copper co-doping causes a decrease in the optical band gap due to a red shift of the fundamental absorption edge.

The description of the fundamental absorption edge of non-conducting solids can be done by Urbach's rule:⁴³

$$\alpha = \alpha_0 e^{\frac{hv}{E_U}} . \quad (7)$$

It is well known that the Urbach energy (E_U) becomes greater as the structural disorder increases and/or the host accumulates more defects.⁴⁴ The E_U values were evaluated through the application of linear regression to the $\ln(\alpha)$ versus hv plots (see Fig. 7 (B)). The obtained Urbach energy shows the same value 0.25 ± 0.02 eV in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses, indicating similar structural disorder in both glasses.

3.4. Photoluminescence spectra

Photoluminescence (PL) spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses registered upon excitation at 401 nm (${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$ transition) are given in Fig. 8. The PL spectra show three strong and one weak bands, which belong to the ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_J$ ($J = 5/2 - 11/2$) transitions of Sm^{3+} ions (see Fig. 8 and Table 3). It should be noted that PL intensity of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass is weaker approximately in 2 – 3 times comparing with the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass. Besides this, the ratio between the emission bands is different. The most intense orange emission band at 597–598 nm (${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$ transition) shows the branching ratio about 0.5 in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses (see Table 3). The branching ratio of the yellow emission band (${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{5/2}$ transition) increases in almost 2 times, whereas the branching ratio of the red emission bands (${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{9/2}$ and ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{11/2}$ transition) decreases in about 2 times in the Cu-Sm co-doped glass comparing with the Sm-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass (Table 3). Thus, the Cu co-doping causes increasing of PL intensity at the yellow wavelengths and decreasing at the red wavelengths. One can also observe a PL signal from 420 nm to 540 nm in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass (see Fig. 8). In our opinion, this PL signal is related to Cu^+ ions.^{14,17,18} The observed PL signal is not an instrumental noise, because the

PL spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass, registered at the same set-up, did not show any PL signal at 420 – 540 nm (see Fig. 8). The Cu^+ PL band is not clearly observed in Fig. 8 because the excitation at 401 nm does not have enough energy to excite the Cu^+ luminescence well.

Photoluminescence excitation (PLE) spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses registered under the monitoring of PL intensity at 597 nm (${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$ transition) are given in Fig. 9. One can observe many narrow excitation bands related to the $4f-4f$ transitions of Sm^{3+} ions. The PLE bands correspond to transitions from the ground ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2}$ level to several excited levels, which are denoted in Fig. 9. The most intense PLE band at 401 – 402 nm belongs to the ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$ transition. It should be noted that the number of Sm^{3+} bands and their resolution are significantly higher in PLE spectra comparing to the optical absorption spectra (compare Fig. 6 and Fig. 9). A weak broad PLE band with a maximum about 270 nm in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass is linked to the $3d^{10} \rightarrow 3d^94s^1$ transition of Cu^+ ions. Comparing PL and PLE spectra, one can observe that PL band of Cu^+ ions under excitation appropriate for Sm^{3+} is stronger than the PLE band of Cu^+ ions under monitoring of the Sm^{3+} emission. This fact indicates that the $\text{Sm}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^+$ energy transfer in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass has a significantly higher probability than the $\text{Cu}^+ \rightarrow \text{Sm}^{3+}$ energy transfer.

In the Fig. 10 are given PL and PLE spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass registered at excitation and monitoring wavelengths of 270 nm and 462 nm, respectively. For comparison, the corresponding PL and PLE spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass are given also in Fig. 10. The PL spectrum of Cu-Sm co-doped glass shows an intense broad (FWHM = 98 nm (4577 cm^{-1})) band peaking at 462 nm. This emission band belongs to the $3d^94s^1 \rightarrow 3d^{10}$ transition of Cu^+ ions. It cannot be ascribed to the divalent Cu. The Cu^{2+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass reveal only a broad absorption peaked at 767 nm and do not show any emission band. It should be noted that the luminescence of Cu^+ ions peaking at 462 nm in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass agrees quite well with corresponding results of published articles.^{45–48} Particularly, the Cu^+ luminescence exhibits a maximum at 460 nm in sodium zinc borate glass⁴⁵, 480 nm in lithium barium borate⁴⁶ and zinc phosphate⁴⁷ glasses, 445 nm in magnesium aluminosilicate glass⁴⁸, and 490 nm in calcium aluminium silicate glass⁴⁸.

The possible process of acquiring of Cu⁺ ions in the Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glass is worth discussing here. The addition of CuO oxide to the glass composition provides Cu²⁺ doping ions. The first mechanism of obtaining of Cu⁺ ions can be based on the thermal decomposition of CuO oxide, which is realized in the air at about 1025°C⁴⁹ via the following chemical reaction:

The Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glass during the melting was heated to more than 1000°C (about 100°C higher than T_{melt} = 917°C for Li₂B₄O₇). Therefore, the glass preparation process led to the reduction of some Cu²⁺ ions to Cu⁺ ions without a reducing agent. The second mechanism of obtaining of Cu⁺ ions can be realized during the glass preparation process at lower temperatures on the basis of structural peculiarities of the investigated borate glasses. Structure of the undoped Li₂B₄O₇ glass was reported previously²² and structure of the Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glass is described in *Subsection 3.1* of this article. According to the structural data, the glass network of the Li₂B₄O₇ and Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glasses consists of tetrahedral BO₄ and triangular BO₃ units. The coordination number of the Li to O in the Li₂B₄O₇²² and Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glasses (see *Subsection 3.1*) varies between 4 and 6. The oxygen atoms in the borate glass network are bridging (represented as B–O–B) and non-bridging (represented as B–O⁻ Li⁺). The Cu²⁺ → Cu⁺ reduction in the Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glass can be expressed as an electron extraction from the non-bridging oxygen to the Cu²⁺ ion in accordance with the following process:

Based on the obtained structural and EPR data, presented above, we can propose that incorporation of Sm³⁺, Cu⁺, and Cu²⁺ ions occurs into the Li⁺ sites of the Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glass network. The B³⁺ ionic radius is extremely small (0.01 Å and 0.11 Å for the three-fold and four-fold coordination, respectively), whereas the Li⁺, Sm³⁺, Cu⁺, and Cu²⁺ ionic radii for the six-fold coordination are close to each other and equal 0.76 Å, 0.958 Å, 0.77 Å, and 0.73 Å, respectively.⁵⁰

As it was obtained above, the ratio of Cu²⁺ amount to total Cu amount in the Li₂B₄O₇:Cu,Sm glass is 43%. In our opinion, the remaining 57% of the Cu dopant is mainly associated with Cu⁺

ions. The obtained results correlate with data^{49,51} in which the $\text{Cu}^+/\text{Cu}_{\text{total}}$ ratio in the range of 48 – 78 % was obtained in bismuth lead oxide glass⁴⁹ and the $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Cu}_{\text{total}}$ ratio in the range of 25 – 66 % was obtained in sodium phosphate glass⁵¹ depending on melting peculiarities.

The weak deep at 401 nm in the PL spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass (see Fig. 10) is related to the ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$ absorption transition of Sm^{3+} ions. Besides this, one can notice a weak emission band at 597 nm, which is ascribed to the ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$ transition of Sm^{3+} ions. In our opinion, presence of the Sm^{3+} luminescence in the orange spectral range is caused by the re-absorption of the Cu^+ blue luminescence rather than by the $\text{Cu}^+ \rightarrow \text{Sm}^{3+}$ energy transfer. The PLE spectrum of main PL band at 462 nm in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass reveals a broad (FWHM = 69 nm (8924 cm^{-1})) band peaking at 270 nm. This PLE band belongs to the $3d^{10} \rightarrow 3d^{10}4s^1$ transition of Cu^+ ions. The PL and PLE bands of Cu^+ ions are not present in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass (Fig. 10).

In the Fig. 11 are given PL and PLE spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass registered at excitation and monitoring wavelengths of 323 nm and 388 nm, respectively. For comparison, the corresponding PL and PLE spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass are given also in Fig. 10. The spectra are focused on the registration of intrinsic luminescence. The intrinsic luminescence in borate glasses has been reported by us.⁵² Particularly, borate glasses upon excitation at 310 – 340 nm show the emission at 360 – 400 nm ascribed to the band-to-band recombination between electrons and holes.⁵²

The $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass under excitation at 323 nm exhibits an intrinsic PL peak at 388 nm (see Fig. 11). A similar intrinsic PL band is observed also in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass. It is also observed that the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass exhibits a strong PL band at 466 nm, which is assigned to the Cu^+ luminescence. The deep in PL spectra at 401 nm is ascribed to the absorption of Sm^{3+} ions (${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$ transition). Three weak PL bands at the orange-red wavelengths are ascribed to the ${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_J$ ($J = 5/2 - 9/2$) transitions of Sm^{3+} ions. Comparing the intensity of Sm^{3+} absorption and emission in the PL spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass (Fig. 11), we propose that the re-absorption mechanism exceeds the $\text{Cu}^+ \rightarrow \text{Sm}^{3+}$ energy transfer. The PLE spectra, indicated by the dashed curves in Fig. 11, were acquired by monitoring the intrinsic PL intensity. The

$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass shows a strong band at 323 nm assigned to intrinsic PLE and a weaker band at 270 nm related to Cu^+ ions. The $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass shows only an intrinsic PLE band.

The nature of the $3d^94s^1 \rightarrow 3d^{10}$ transition of Cu^+ ions should be discussed more. The ground energy state of Cu^+ ions is $^1\text{S}_0$ ($3d^{10}$ electron configuration). The excited $3d^94s^1$ electron configuration creates the $^3\text{D}_3$, $^3\text{D}_2$, $^3\text{D}_1$, and $^1\text{D}_2$ states. But, such splitting (known as spin-orbital) is possible if Cu^+ ions are almost free in the network of investigated glass. In accordance with EPR and optical absorption spectroscopy it can be assumed that Cu^+ ions, likewise Cu^{2+} ions, are in a distorted octahedral configuration. As a consequence, the crystal field splitting is dominant over the spin-orbital splitting. Consequently, the $^1\text{S}_0$ ground level converts to the $^1\text{A}_g$ state, the ^3D term splits onto the $^3\text{E}_g$ and $^3\text{T}_{2g}$ states, and the ^1D term splits onto the $^1\text{E}_g$ and $^1\text{T}_{2g}$ states.⁵³ Therefore, the observed blue PL of Cu^+ ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass can be assigned to the $^3\text{E}_g \rightarrow ^1\text{A}_g$ transition, which has the lowest energy.

Let's go shortly back to Cu^{2+} ions with the intense broad absorption (see Fig. 6). Unfortunately, all attempts to record PL and/or PLE spectra of Cu^{2+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass were unsuccessful. The excited Cu^{2+} ions return non-radiatively to the ground state and do not show any PL signals in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass. The lack of Cu^{2+} luminescence makes a detailed analysis of the energy transfer to Cu^{2+} ions difficult.

The CIE diagram is shown in Fig. 12 to illustrate the emitted colors. The symbol “•” labeled by (a) corresponds to the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass under excitation with a wavelength of 401 nm, whereas the symbols “•” labeled by (b), (c) and (d) letters represent the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass excited at 401 nm, 270 nm, and 323 nm, respectively. The emitted color of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass upon excitation with a wavelength of 401 nm is shifted from the orange to the yellow spectral range comparing with the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass due to changes in the luminescence branching ratio of the $^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6\text{H}_{5/2-11/2}$ transitions. Besides this, one can see that the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass offers a wide range of emitted color tuning from blue to yellow via changes in the excitation wavelength.

3.5. Analysis of the photoluminescence decay kinetics

The PL decay kinetics of the Sm^{3+} emission in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses are shown in Fig. 13. Obtained curves cannot be satisfactorily fitted by a mono-exponential decay. Consequently, the mean lifetime was calculated as follows:

$$\tau_{\text{mean}} = \frac{\int t \cdot I(t) \cdot dt}{\int I(t) \cdot dt} \quad (10)$$

where $I(t)$ is dependence of the PL intensity on the time t . Obtained τ_{mean} values equal 1.06 ms and 2.64 ms in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glasses, respectively. Thus, the Cu co-doping leads to a considerable shortening (in 2.5 times) of the Sm^{3+} lifetime. It is caused by energy transfer from the Sm^{3+} ions to the Cu dopant. The efficiency of the energy transfer (η) can be estimated according to the Förster theory⁵⁴ via the following formula:

$$\eta = 1 - \frac{\tau_{DA}}{\tau_D}, \quad (11)$$

where τ_{DA} and τ_D are lifetimes of donors in the presence and absence of acceptors, respectively. The obtained value $\eta = 59.8\%$ confirms the efficient energy transfer from Sm^{3+} ions to Cu centers.

The PL decay kinetics of Sm^{3+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass was analyzed by Inokuti–Hirayama model⁵⁵ (see inset in Fig. 13). According to this model, PL decay curve accompanied by the energy transfer from donors to acceptors is described as follows:

$$I(t) = I_0 \exp \left(-\frac{t}{\tau_0} - Q \left(\frac{t}{\tau_0} \right)^{\frac{3}{S}} \right), \quad (12)$$

where I_0 is the beginning intensity of PL, τ_0 is the lifetime of donors in the absence of acceptors ($\tau_0 = 2.64$ ms in our case), S is the parameter, which indicates the dipole-dipole interaction for $S = 6$, the dipole-quadrupole interaction for $S = 8$ or the quadrupole-quadrupole interaction for $S = 10$. The energy transfer parameter (Q) is determined by the formula:

$$Q = \frac{4\pi}{3} \Gamma \left(1 - \frac{3}{S} \right) N_A R_0^3, \quad (13)$$

where $\Gamma(1-3/S)$ is the gamma function ($\Gamma(0.5) \approx 1.773$ for $S = 6$, $\Gamma(0.625) \approx 1.435$ for $S = 8$, and

$\Gamma(0.7) \approx 1.299$ for $S = 10$), N_A is the number of acceptors per unit volume ($N_A = 1.123 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ in our case), R_0 is the distance between donors and acceptors at which the energy transfer rate is equal to the spontaneous emission rate.⁵⁵

Results of fitting of experimental decay curve by the Inokuti–Hirayama formula with different S are given as an inset in Fig. 13. The most accurate fit was obtained with $S = 6$. This fact suggests that the energy transfer occurs due to the electric dipole-dipole interaction. Fitting gives the following values of energy transfer parameter (Q) and critical transfer distance (R_0): $Q = 1.836$ and $R_0 = 19.96 \text{ \AA}$.

Generally, the mean distance between randomly distributed acceptor ions can be roughly evaluated as follows:

$$R_{Cu-Cu} = \left(\frac{3}{4\pi N_A} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}, \quad (14)$$

where N_A is the concentration of acceptors. The mean distance between Cu doping ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass according to Eq. (14) equals 12.86 \AA . The mean distance between donors (Sm^{3+} ions) and acceptors (Cu^+ and Cu^{2+} ions) in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass is less in 2 times and equals 6.43 \AA . This value is significantly lower than the obtained R_0 distance. Hence, the rate of energy transfer is considerably much higher than the rate of radiative emission.

The PL decay kinetics of the Cu^+ emission in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass is shown in Fig. 14. The decay curve is strongly non-single exponential and was quite well fitted by a double exponential function with lifetime values of 34 \mu s and 107 \mu s . The amplitude-weighted average lifetime (τ_{avg}) was determined with use of the following expression:

$$\tau_{\text{avg}} = \frac{A_1\tau_1 + A_2\tau_2}{A_1 + A_2}, \quad (15)$$

where A_1 and A_2 represent the amplitudes of the τ_1 and τ_2 lifetime, respectively. The calculated τ_{avg} lifetime equals 69 \mu s . It is worth mentioning that a single exponential function with a lifetime of 23 \mu s is exhibited by Cu^+ ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ glass¹⁴. Thus, a prolongation of the Cu^+ decay time is registered in the Cu-Sm co-doped glass comparing with the Cu-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass.

Quenching of the Sm^{3+} PL intensity, shortening of the Sm^{3+} lifetime and prolongation of the

Cu^+ lifetime in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass are connected with the excitation energy transfer from Sm^{3+} ions (donors) to Cu^+ ions (acceptors). Quenching of the Sm^{3+} PL intensity can be related also to the re-absorption of the Sm^{3+} emission by Cu^{2+} ions. The absence of Cu^{2+} luminescence makes it impossible to confirm the $\text{Sm}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{2+}$ energy transfer by luminescence decay kinetics techniques. Let us consider these two mechanisms (see Fig. 15). The excitation energy in the UV-violet range is transferred from Sm^{3+} ions to Cu^+ ions with subsequent emission at 462 – 466 nm (left part of the Fig. 15). Besides this, the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass shows the strong broadband absorption of Cu^{2+} ions in the 540 – 740 nm spectral range, where the Sm^{3+} luminescence has been observed (see Figs. 6 and 8). As a consequence, the part of Sm^{3+} emission is re-absorbed by Cu^{2+} ions. The Cu^{2+} ions then relax non-radiatively to the ground state (right part of the Fig. 15). From our point of view, the second mechanism, involving the re-absorption from Sm^{3+} ions to Cu^{2+} ions, is stronger in the investigated $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass.

4. Conclusions

The Cu-Sm co-doped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ ($\text{Li}_2\text{O}-2\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$) glass has been obtained and studied in detail with the use of XRD, EPR and optical spectroscopy techniques. Obtained results were compared with corresponding data for the Sm-doped and Cu-doped glasses with the same basic composition. It is found that Cu and Sm dopants are incorporated into the structure of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass as Sm^{3+} ($4f^5$), Cu^+ ($3d^{10}$) and Cu^{2+} ($3d^9$) ions. The BO_n ($n = 3 - 4$) and LiO_n ($n = 4 - 6$) units dominate in the network of the investigated glass. The EPR spectrum shows a characteristic axially-symmetric signal of Cu^{2+} ions. The Cu^{2+} cations and O^{2-} anions compose the elongated octahedrons in the network of $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass. The optical absorption spectrum shows a very broad intense band ascribed to the ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$, ${}^2\text{B}_{2g}$, ${}^2\text{E}_g$ transitions of Cu^{2+} ions and a lot of weaker narrow bands assigned to the ${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{7/2}$, ${}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$, ${}^4\text{I}_{9/2-15/2}$, ${}^6\text{F}_{9/2}$, ${}^6\text{F}_{7/2}$, ${}^6\text{F}_{5/2}$ transitions of Sm^{3+} ions. The PL and PLE spectra and PL decay kinetics of Sm^{3+} and Cu^+ ions in the Cu-Sm co-doped glass were registered, analysed, and discussed. In particular, the PL spectra exhibit a very broad band in the blue spectral range ascribed to the $3d^9 4s^1 \rightarrow 3d^{10}$ transition of Cu^+ ions and four narrow bands in

the yellow-red spectral range assigned to the ${}^4G_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_J$ ($J = 5/2 - 11/2$) transitions of Sm^{3+} ions. The PL decay kinetics of Sm^{3+} and Cu^+ ions in the Cu-Sm co-doped glass are non-single exponential and characterized by a mean lifetime in the ms and μs time ranges, respectively. Quenching of the Sm^{3+} PL intensity, shortening of the Sm^{3+} decay time and prolongation of the Cu^+ decay time were observed in the Cu-Sm co-doped glass by way of comparison with the Sm-doped and Cu-doped glasses. The energy transfer and re-absorption processes from Sm^{3+} ions to Cu^+ and Cu^{2+} ions have been discussed. The ratio of Cu^{2+} amount to total Cu amount was determined that equals $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Cu}_{\text{total}} = 43\%$. A wide range of emission colors from blue to yellow is achieved in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu},\text{Sm}$ glass by varying of the excitation wavelength.

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Authors' declarations

There are no conflicts of interest to declare

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Table 1. Average $r_{\text{B-O}}$ and $r_{\text{Li-O}}$ interatomic distances and $N_{\text{B-O}}$ and $N_{\text{Li-O}}$ coordination numbers in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass. The interatomic distances and coordination numbers in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass were determined with uncertainties of 0.003 nm and 0.3, respectively. The local structure parameters for undoped $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass²² and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal²⁴ are presented for comparison with corresponding data obtained for $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass.

Material	$r_{\text{B-O}}$ [nm]	$N_{\text{B-O}}$	$r_{\text{Li-O}}$ [nm]	$N_{\text{Li-O}}$
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass (this article)	0.155	3.0 4.0	0.259	4.5
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ glass ²²	0.165	3.5	0.279	4.4
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal ²⁴	0.1355;0.1371; 0.1374; $r_{\text{B-O}}^{\text{av}} = 0.1367$ 0.1453;0.1506; 0.1502;0.1454; $r_{\text{B-O}}^{\text{av}} = 0.1479$	3.0 4.0	0.2061	4.0

Table 2. Axial g -tensor components (g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp}), axial A -tensor components (A_{\parallel} , A_{\perp}), and peak-to-peak linewidths ($\Delta H_{pp}^{\parallel}$, ΔH_{pp}^{\perp}) for Cu^{2+} centres at $T = 295$ K, which were derived from EPR spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass and the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ glasses with 0.4 mol.%^{14,15} and 1.6 mol.%¹⁶ of the CuO dopant.

Glass	CuO content [mol.%]	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{\parallel} [Gs]	A_{\perp} [Gs]	$\Delta H_{pp}^{\parallel}$ [Gs]	ΔH_{pp}^{\perp} [Gs]
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ (this article)	1.0	2.34(7)	2.06(3)	141.0±0.5	21.5±0.5	49.0±0.5	17.5±0.5
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ ^{14,15}	0.4	2.34±0.05	2.06±0.05	142.8±0.5	23.4±0.5	51.1±0.5	18.0±0.5
$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu}$ ¹⁶	1.6	2.30±0.05	2.07±0.05	144.5±0.5	26.9±0.5	53.8±0.5	20.7±0.5

Table 3. Position of maximum (λ_{\max}), full width at half maximum (FWHM) and branching ratio (β) of the Sm^{3+} PL bands in $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}^{13}$ glasses.

Transition	$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$			$\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}^{13}$		
	λ_{\max} [nm]	FWHM [cm^{-1}]	β	λ_{\max} [nm]	FWHM [cm^{-1}]	β
${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{5/2}$	561	294	0.390	562	289	0.210
${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$	597	235	0.494	598	281	0.549
${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{9/2}$	644	316	0.105	645	271	0.218
${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{11/2}$	703	508	0.011	705	553	0.022

Captions for Figures

- Fig. 1.** Investigated samples of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (a) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ (b) glasses.
- Fig. 2.** Experimental XRD pattern (black circles) and smoothed XRD profile (red line) of the investigated $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass as well as referenced data for the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ crystal (blue line) and SiO_2 crystal (magenta line) as a function of the modulus of the scattering vector s .
- Fig. 3.** Calculated radial distribution function and its deconvolution with indication of obtained most probable interatomic distances in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass network.
- Fig. 4.** The X-band EPR spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass, registered at $T = 295$ K in wide (A) and narrow (B) ranges of magnetic field.
- Fig. 5.** Experimental (a) and simulated (b) EPR spectra of Cu^{2+} ions in $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass.
- Fig. 6.** Optical absorption spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ (red curve (a)) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (black curve (b)) glasses, registered at $T = 295$ K.
- Fig. 7.** Plots for the determination of the optical band gap (E_g^{opt}) and Urbach energy (E_U) in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ (a) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (b) glasses.
- Fig. 8.** The PL spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ (a) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (b) glasses, registered at $T = 295$ K under excitation with $\lambda_{exc} = 401$ nm (${}^6\text{H}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{P}_{3/2}$ transition).
- Fig. 9.** The PLE spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ (a) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (b) glasses, registered at $T = 295$ K by monitoring at $\lambda_{mon} = 597$ nm (${}^4\text{G}_{5/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$ transition).
- Fig. 10.** The PL (solid curves) and PLE (dashed curves) spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ (a) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (b) glasses at $T = 295$ K. Excitation (λ_{exc}) and monitoring (λ_{mon}) wavelengths are denoted in the Figure.
- Fig. 11.** The PL (solid curves) and PLE (dashed curves) spectra of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ (a) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (b) glasses at $T = 295$ K. Excitation (λ_{exc}) and monitoring (λ_{mon}) wavelengths are denoted in the Figure.
- Fig. 12.** The CIE diagram, where the symbols “•” labeled as (a), (b), (c) and (d) represent the emission color of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ glass under excitation at 401 nm and the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass under excitation at 401 nm, 270 nm, and 323 nm, respectively.
- Fig. 13.** The PL decay kinetics of Sm^{3+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ (a) and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Sm}$ (b) glasses at $T = 295$ K. Inset shows the PL decay curve of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass that is fitted by the Inokuti-Hirayama model with S values equal 6, 8, and 10.
- Fig. 14.** The PL decay kinetics of Cu^+ ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass at $T = 295$ K.
- Fig. 15.** Partial energy level diagram for Sm^{3+} , Cu^+ , and Cu^{2+} ions in the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Cu,Sm}$ glass demonstrating PL and PLE mechanisms as well as energy transfer and re-absorption channels.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4 (A)

Fig. 4 (B)

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 10

Fig. 12

Fig. 13

Fig. 14

Fig. 15

